

DASTURLASH TILLARI VA PYTHON DASTURLASH TILINI O'RNATISH

Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti, 1-bosqich magistrant.

maqsudu32@gmail.com

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ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada dasturlash tillari, Python dasturlash tilini o'rnatish, o'rganish va qo'llashning soddaligi, mukammal kutubxonaning mavjudligi, Pythonda o'zgaruvchilarni tavsiflash, Pythonda xatoliklar bilan ishlash, Pythonda ma'lumot turlari, Python dasturlash tili kutubxonasi haqida batafsil bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: dasturlash, kompyuter dasturi, dasturchi, Python, identifikator, IDLE, o'zgaruvchilarni tavsiflash.

Bugungi kunda ijtimoiy hayotning qaysi jabhasini ko'rmasligimizdan qat'iy nazar, kompyuterlashtirish jarayoni hamma joyda tez sur'atlar bilan kechayotganini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Endi telefon nafaqat gaplashadigan qurilma, balki u matn, audio, video xabarlar yuborishi, shuningdek, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali muloqot qilishi mumkin.

Zamon talabi o'quvchilarimizga nafaqat ushbu qurilma va texnologiyalardan foydalanishni bilish, balki ularni dasturlash yordamida ishlab chiqish va raqamlashtirishni ham qiyinlashtirmoqda.

Kompyuter dasturi - bu masalani hal qilish uchun kompyuter tomonidan bajarilishi kerak bo'lgan ketma-ket buyruqlar to'plami. Dasturlash - bu kompyuter uchun dastur yaratish jarayoni. Dasturchi - bu dastur ishlab chiquvchi shaxs.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Ma'lumki, kompyuter turli masalalarni yechishda foydalanuvchining eng yaqin yordamchisi hisoblanadi. Xususan, matn, grafik muharrirlar, taqdimot dasturlari, elektron jadvallar kabi insonlarga qulaylik yaratish maqsadida ko'plab ilovalar ishlab chiqilgan. Shuningdek, ta'lim, bank, soliq, huquq va tibbiyot uchun maxsus ishlab chiqilgan kompyuter dasturlari mavjud.

Kompyuterda masalani yechish uchun eng avvalo uning modeli va algoritmi tuziladi, so'ngra bu algoritm kompyuter ma'lum qoidalar asosida tushunadigan va ma'lum alifbodan foydalanib yoziladigan ko'rsatmalar va buyruqlarga aylantiriladi. Yaratilgan matn kompyuter tilida yozilgan dastur deb ataladi.

Kompyuter dasturi - bu masalani hal qilish uchun kompyuter bajarishi kerak bo'lgan ko'rsatmalar ketma-ketligi. Kompyuter dasturi har kim tez o'rganishi

mumkin bo'lgan chet tiliga o'xshaydi. Odamlar kabi, kompyuterlar ham o'z tilida muloqot qilishadi. Bu lug'at boyligi cheklangan va imlo qoidalarining qat'iy bo'lgan faqat kompyuter tili. Kompyuter tushunadigan va muloqot qila oladigan "til"ga dasturlash tili deyiladi. Har qanday dasturlash tilini biladigan har bir kishi osongina o'z dasturini yaratishi mumkin.

Ko'pgina dasturlash tillari mavjud bo'lib, ularning har biri muayyan muammolarni hal qilish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Python dasturlash tili ularning eng mashhurlaridan biridir. Python veb-saytlar, ilovalar va o'yinlar yaratish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan ilg'or dasturiy mahsulotlarni yaratish uchun dunyodagi eng mashhur dasturlash tillaridan biridir.

NATIJALAR

O'rganish va qo'llashning soddaligi. Python sodda va qulay dasturlash tili bo'lib, boshqa dasturlash tillariga nisbatan uning yordamida dastur tuzish qiyinchilik tug'dirmaydi.

Mukammal kutubxonaning mavjudligi. Pythonda dastur tuzish jarayonida kutubxonadagi tayyor funksiyalardan foydalanish mumkin. Bu esa murakkab dasturlarni ham qisqa vaqtda tuzish imkonini beradi.

Python dasturlash tilini o'rganish uchun uni o'zining rasmiy saytidan yuklab olib, keyin o'rnatish zarur. Python kompyuterga IDLE dasturi bilan birga o'rnatiladi.

IDLE dasturlashni endi boshlaganlar uchun mo'ljallangan IDE bo'lib, kod yozish uchun uncha murakkab bo'lmagan matn muharriri hamda dastur natijasi va xatolarni ko'rsatib turuvchi oynaga ega.

Har bir tilning alifbosi bo'lgani kabi dasturlash tilining ham o'z alifbosi mavjud. Python dasturlash tilining alifbosi katta va kichik lotin harflari, arab raqamlari, maxsus belgilar va xizmatchi so'zlardan tarkib topgan. Odatda, dasturlar kiritilgan ma'lumotlarni qabul qilish, qayta ishlash, shuningdek, natijani ekranga chiqarish uchun mo'ljallangan bo'ladi.

O'zgaruvchilar - o'z qiymati va turiga ega kattalik, o'zida qiymatlarni saqlaydigan kompyuter xotirasidagi yacheyka nomi. O'zgaruvchining qiymatlari dastur davomida o'zgarib turishi mumkin. Doimiy (o'zgarimas) - faqat o'qish uchun mo'ljallangan qiymatlarni saqlovchi kompyuter xotirasidagi yacheyka nomi. Doimiylar o'zgaruvchilar kabi o'z qiymati va turiga ega. Identifikatorlar - o'zgaruvchilar, doimiylar, funksiyalar, protseduralar, modullar, dasturlarning umumiy nomi.

Dasturlarni yozishda o'zida asosiy ma'lumotlarni saqlaydigan o'zgaruvchi yoki doimiylardan foydalaniladi. O'zgaruvchilar dastur jarayonida o'zgarishi mumkin

bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni belgilaydi, doimiydan esa o'zgarimas ma'lumotlar uchun foydalaniladi. O'zgaruvchilar va doimiylarni belgilash uchun turli nomlar, ya'ni identifikator (identification)lardan foydalaniladi.

MUHOKAMA

Har qanday dasturni yozish jarayonida turli xatolarga yo'l qo'yilishi mumkin. Yozilgan dasturda xatolik bo'lsa, dastur ishga tushmaydi va ekranda xato xabari paydo bo'ladi. Ma'lumki, axborot matnli, raqamli, audio, grafik va boshqa shakllarda uzatilishi mumkin. Bunday ma'lumotlarni dasturlash tillarida qayta ishlash uchun ularni turlarga bo'lish kerak.

Dasturda qo'llaniladigan ma'lumotlar turlari dasturning maqsadiga bog'liq: oddiy kalkulyator raqamlardan foydalanadi va elektron pochta manzillarini tekshirish uchun mo'ljallangan dastur matn bilan ishlaydi. Sonlar natural, butun va haqiqiy sonlarga bo'linadi. Matnli ma'lumotlar belgilar yoki satrlardan iborat bo'lishi mumkin.

Ma'lumotlar turi - bu o'zgaruvchi yoki doimiy qiymatlardagi ma'lumotlar shakli. Ma'lumotlar turi kompyuter xotirasida yetarlicha joyini zaxiraga olib qo'yish uchun kerak bo'ladi. Odatda, dasturlash tillarida ma'lumotlar turi o'zgaruvchi yoki doimiy bilan birga e'lon qilinadi.

Python dinamik turlarga ajratuvchi dasturlash tili hisoblanadi. Shu sababli, Pythonda o'zgaruvchining turi u foydalanayotgan qiymat bo'yicha belgilanadi, lekin ma'lumot turini boshqa turga o'zgartirish uchun tur ko'rsatilishi shart.

XULOSA

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish joizki, har bir yangi dasturning kodini yozish ko'p vaqt talab qiladigan jarayon hisoblanadi. Shu sababli, tayyor qism dasturlardan foydalanish har bir dasturchi uchun qulaydir. Zamonaviy dasturlash tillarida bu jarayonni yengillashtirish uchun tayyor dastur kodlarini saqlovchi kutubxonalar mavjud.

Boshqa dasturlash tillari kabi Python dasturlash tilining standart kutubxonasi ham ko'plab tayyor kod fragmentlari (modullar, standart funksiyalar va b.)dan tarkib topgan.

Python dasturlash tili o'rnatgichidagi Batteries included (батарейки в комплекте - batareykasi bilan) izohi Python dasturlash tili majmuida ko'plab tayyor kodlar mavjudligini anglatadi. Python dasturlash tilini yanada takomillashtirish uchun foydalanuvchi tomonidan yozilgan modullarni kutubxonaning alohida qismiga yuklash ham mumkin

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